

REFLECTIONS ON TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10116625**Suiane Costa Alves**

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ABSTRACT

Currently, we are being invited to reflect on education in its multiple aspects and, in this regard, the continued training of teachers seeks to promote methodological didacticization and educational practices, leading to the most varied perspectives of expanding learning and intellectual production frameworks. That said, this work discusses Continuing Teacher Training, culminating in the presentation of the training project for teachers in the area of Natural Sciences.

Keywords: Continuing Teacher Training; Natural Sciences; Project-Based Learning.

INTRODUCTION

One of the challenges of Science Teaching is the link between the knowledge shared in the classroom and the daily lives of students. As Natural Sciences are an agent of social change, they are capable of helping the student to improve their knowledge, as it provides intellectual

development, the understanding of concepts and methodological procedures associated with attitudes and values, promoting the search for understanding of nature and its transformation, through the production of experiments.

Sometimes, the presentation of the contents of this area remains distant from the student's reality, which makes it difficult to understand. According to Fazenda (2007), the curriculum of traditional subjects, as it has been developed in school units, offers only the accumulation of information that is little or not relevant to the exercise of citizenship and the world of work, as it is primarily focused on memorization of information. Various academic research shows that the use of appropriate methodology, with different approaches, influences the teaching and learning process. When incorporated into pedagogical praxis, they end up helping students understand the concepts.

According to Frigotto (2011), the specialism in teacher training and the activism that prevails in pedagogical work is the result of fragmented training that constitutes an obstacle to interdisciplinary work. In this dialogue, investment in continued training is necessary.

According to Lima and Alves (2022), interdisciplinary and contextualized work is necessary for students to better understand the content. One of the objectives of continuing education is to provide educators with the exchange of experiences that can be facilitated by face-to-face and/or virtual meetings.

For Cachapuz et al. (2005) cited by Alves (2023, p. 60), "Science Teaching must promote the understanding of natural and social reality, elucidating the importance of global citizenship, transforming and impacting curricula".

Among the objectives of face-to-face meetings, we can mention the mediation of the University training process through the sharing of speeches, presences and experiences, promoting professional qualification. Therefore, it is expected that the meetings will be spaces that suit the needs of teachers and the knowledge can be used in school units.

action is reflected in the classroom, when coming into contact with new ideas and perspectives for Science Teaching. According to Japiassú (1976), the interdisciplinary attitude is motivated by the feeling of discovering the "new", promoting the redefinition of knowledge that is often presented in a fragmented way and without connection with the students' daily reality. Thus, teaching and learning in Natural Sciences consists of the need for scientific education for all citizens, promoting scientific literacy through interdisciplinary work.

The commitment to comprehensive education proposes overcoming disciplinary fragmentation, encouraging application in real life, the importance of context in giving meaning to what is learned and the protagonism of students in their learning and in the construction of

their life project. The concept of Integral Education, to which the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) is committed, refers to the construction of educational processes that promote learning based on the needs of students in the face of the challenges of contemporary society (BRASIL, 2018).

That said, the objective of this work is to identify the potential of face-to-face meetings of municipal trainers from the MAIS PAIC Sciences Program of the municipal education network linked to the 1st Regional Coordination for Education Development (CREDE 1). The course promoted in 2019 aimed to carry out a training process in the area of Natural Sciences, having primarily served municipal trainers and science teachers from the municipal education network who work in the classroom.

The actions developed included dialogue on the challenges of Science Teaching, curriculum and assessment, use of different learning methodologies, dialogue on integral education and socio-emotional skills, as well as laboratory practices with alternative material, aiming at the sustainability of natural resources, addressing concepts and theories in a contextualized and interdisciplinary way as established by the BNCC. The data were collected from the analysis of meetings that included the participation of trainers from the municipalities of Aquiraz, Caucaia, Eusébio, Guaiúba, Itaitinga, Maracanaú, Maranguape and Pacatuba.

CONTINUING TEACHER TRAINING AND THE MAIS PAIC PROGRAM

School failure has been the subject of discussions by State and Municipal Education Departments that seek to develop propositions in search of paths that point out alternatives for understanding and overcoming it. To understand school failure it is necessary to evaluate its multiple aspects. Patto (1990) is emphatic in confirming the complexity of school failure as it involves socioeconomic, ideological, political, historical, institutional and pedagogical dimensions. Starting in the 90s of the last century, Brazilian education began to improve its evaluation process in search of alternatives and improvement of proficiency indicators.

The State of Ceará was a pioneer in carrying out the first evaluation of the Ceará Permanent Basic Education Assessment System (SPAECE) in 1992. The National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira (INEP) uses Item Response Theory (IRT) to obtain the proficiency scales of the evaluated students, in which the proficiencies order the students' performance from lowest to highest. With this method it is possible to evaluate what students know and/or understand about basic content and which methods can be used during the teaching and learning process in order to help consolidate knowledge. Through this

evaluation system, it is possible to place the data at a performance scale level, as well as demonstrate the skills described in the previous levels of this scale through the statistical results verified in the evaluations.

In 2011, the State of Ceará understood that it was necessary to radically change and in the shortest possible time the worrying situation of the low level of student learning, through the Association of Mayors of the State of Ceará (Aprece) and the Union of Municipal Directors of Ceará (Undime/CE), with the support of UNICEF, made a commitment to the municipalities to continue the actions developed by the Cearense Committee for the Elimination of School Illiteracy, giving rise to the Literacy at the Right Age Program (PAIC). Continuing with the implementation of the program, In 2015, the Department of Education of the State of Ceará (SEDUC) initiated a MAIS PAIC Continuing Training Program for all 6th and 9th year teachers from all 184 municipalities in the State in the subjects of Portuguese and Mathematics and from 2019 the inclusion of the Natural Sciences discipline.

In this context, the MAIS PAIC Program emerges as a cooperative action between the state and municipalities in order to provide teachers with moments to exchange experiences among other actions in order to develop goals that can impact the daily life of the classroom, promoting in students the development of skills and abilities necessary to promote student protagonism, intellectual autonomy, exercise of citizenship and continuation of studies. We emphasize that, in the discipline of Natural Sciences, for an effective grasp of scientific knowledge it is important to consider the experiences already experienced by students and the universe in which they are inserted.

Combined with the material proposed by the MAIS PAIC Program, educators must also take advantage of the current moment of technological profusion, with a view to carrying out a process of modernization of teaching and learning practices, whether in the pedagogical format or in the content offered. This must occur with the purpose of meeting the current demands implied by the dynamization and globalization of the modern world (AMARAL; AMARAL, 2008).

METHODOLOGY

In this work, we chose to carry out a case study research that focuses on collecting information. According to Yin (2001), the case study is a study of events within their real-life contexts. Therefore, data must be collected from existing people and institutions and not within the controlled confines of a laboratory or through questionnaires with a rigid structure. The

approach to analyzing the results was qualitative. The qualitative approach is characterized by knowledge or contact with a direct source of data, by the descriptive nature and observation of the meanings that people give to things, as well as by the inductive approach. According to Neves (1996), the development of a qualitative research study presupposes a temporal-spatial cut of a certain phenomenon on the part of the researcher. We then present a qualitative analysis of the participation of municipal trainers in the proposed activities.

The analysis of the proposed activities was important to evaluate participation in face-to-face training meetings. Therefore, in this research we divided the activities into experimental practices, discussions and conversation circles whose objective is to add information to strengthen the continuing education process and its impact on students' learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the participation of municipal trainers in the proposed course was analyzed. As mentioned previously, we categorized the activities of face-to-face meetings into experimental practices, discussions and conversation circles in which course participants talked to each other about the topics at hand.

The face-to-face meetings took place monthly at the 1st Regional Education Development Coordination (CREDE 1) located in the municipality of Maracanaú/CE between April and October 2019. Municipal trainers replicated the training for municipal teachers with the support of the Municipal Education Departments (SME). Throughout the training course, an average of two hundred and fifty science teachers participated, generating transformations in the classroom and its impact on the teaching and learning process of students.

Among the agendas of the meetings, we highlight the dialogue on the Ceará Reference Curriculum Document (DCRC), Integral Education and Socio-Emotional Competencies, curriculum, methodologies, evaluation and experimental practices in Science Teaching (biology, physics and chemistry), astronomy olympics and astronautics, rocket journeys, scientific initiation and project development.

Based on the theme of Integral Education and Socio-Emotional Skills, regional psychologists Soraia Cassiano and Talitha Lousada addressed the five socio-emotional macro-skills that outline the path to full development, preparing students to make choices regarding behaviors related to themselves and others, observed in the sequence: (1) Self-management; (2) Openness to the new; (3) Agreeableness; (4) Emotional Resilience; (5) Engagement with others (ALVES, *et. al.* 2022).

In relation to the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) and the Ceará Reference Curriculum Document (DCRC), we sought to discuss the new curricular proposal for Science Teaching, as well as the internal and external evaluation processes. As the BNCC is a document of a normative nature in promoting essential learning, it is clear that the curricula identify with each other in the commonality of principles and values as guided by the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB) and the National Curricular Guidelines (DCN), promoting commitment to training and human development. (BRAZIL, 2018)

Regarding Pedagogical Aspects in the Development of Scientific Initiation in Basic Education, Experimental Practices in Science Teaching (Figure 1), Astronomy and Astronautics Olympiad, Rocket Journey, we seek to discuss pedagogical aspects of the scientific development of Basic Education, promoting the dialogue about the importance of student leadership in the development of projects, in a conceptual and practical way.

Figure 1: Production of a Dark Chamber and Inorganic Functions with the Production of Salts

Source: Direct Search

From this reflection, we can see the importance of scientific initiation and the development of projects in basic education, whose action must be linked to the exercise of citizenship, continuation of studies and/or the world of work, including ethical training, as well as intellectual autonomy of the student, as established by the BNCC and observed in the report of the municipal trainer:

“When working on research projects, we encourage curiosity, empathy and assertiveness. Through projects, we develop enriching skills and competencies in our students, motivating them to work as a team. We thus provide new ways of learning, encouraging participation.” (Report from a Municipal Trainer).

“Project-Based Learning, also known as Project Based Learning, constitutes an active methodology that focuses on the development of problem-solving skills, exercising protagonism in personal and collective life” (SANTOS et al., 2021 apud ALVES, 2023 , p. 60).

Professor Catarina Almeida's lecture on the Cooperative Learning (CA) methodology aimed to present it as a tool that enhances learning through the motivation of those who teach and those who learn, where its application promotes reflection on knowledge as a collective construction in the student. Thus, students who find it easier to grasp the content have the opportunity to help their colleagues with greater difficulty, as reported by a municipal trainer: “ Cooperative learning encourages students to work as a team, worrying not only about their own learning , but also with the learning of your colleague”. (Report from a Municipal Trainer).

In relation to percentage data, the training course had the participation of all municipal trainers who evaluated the training journey as 100% satisfactory in relation to the methodology used, pedagogical material used, where the contents covered are relevant to teaching practice, the compliance with the agenda and workload, as well as the trainer’s mastery of the content.

Given the current educational reality, this research sought to highlight the importance of continued training, proposing Science Teaching beyond the mere transmission of knowledge, showing the importance of the student in the process of building training, sharing speeches and experiences, encouraging other teachers cooperation, sharing and gratitude.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Reflections surrounding the continuing education process have been deepened in recent years given the realization of its influence on the search for a pedagogical practice based on collaborative work, contributing to the formation of interdisciplinary teams. In this context, the training meetings aimed to deepen knowledge, enabling greater interaction between the agents of this construction process. As for the research field, the application was carried out at the 1st Regional Coordination for Education Development (CREDE 1), involving municipal trainers and natural science teachers. The research made it possible to identify the potential of each municipality, as well as the points that are still challenges, proposing strategies to strengthen pedagogical actions.

Faced with these challenges, this research proposes science teaching based on interdisciplinary work, motivating student protagonism and an education focused on the exercise of citizenship and the resolution of problem situations that arise in local and global

communities so that students become responsible and ethical citizens, reflecting and seeking solutions to issues that are characterized as planetary emergency situations.

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